

21GRD07 PlasticTrace

Deliverable 6

Paper on the developed characterisation methods for SMPs ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$) and NPs ($< 0.1 \mu\text{m}$), and in terms of: (i) chemical identity of the SMPs/NPs polymer type; (ii) physical particle characterisation and quantification, size distribution and particle morphologies; and (iii) quantification of the mass fraction in complex matrices.

Uncertainty evaluation and traceability statements will be included

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable:

LGC Limited (LGC)

Due date of the deliverable: 01.07.2025

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 30.09.2025

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open

Deliverable Cover Sheet

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EURAMET. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

Executive Summary

Reliable reference and quality control materials are essential for advancing the measurement and risk assessment of nanoplastics. However, materials with physicochemical properties comparable to those of real environmental and food contaminants are still lacking. Within this work, presented in the paper *"Multiparameter characterisation of a nano-polypropylene representative test material with fractionation, light scattering, high-resolution microscopy, spectroscopy, and spectrometry methods"*, we describe the development and comprehensive characterisation of a polypropylene nanoplastic material produced through a top-down mechanical fragmentation process. The material is homogeneous, stable in suspension, and representative of environmental nanoplastics.

A wide range of analytical techniques — including AF4, cFFF, PTA, (MA)DLS, MALS, SEM, AFM, TEM, STEM, EDS, Raman, ICP-MS and py-GC/MS — were employed to determine its particle size and distribution, particle number concentration, polymer identity, mass fraction, and inorganic impurity content. Results show a broad size distribution (50–200 nm), consistent polypropylene composition with signs of surface oxidation, and trace levels of inorganic impurities. The study demonstrates how complementary measurement approaches can be combined to improve the reliability, uncertainty evaluation, and traceability of nanoplastics characterisation. This work directly contributes to the PlasticTrace deliverable *"Paper on the developed characterisation methods for SMPs (<10 µm) and NPs (<0.1 µm)"*, addressing the chemical identification, physical characterisation, and quantification of nanoplastic materials, and providing a reference framework for harmonised and comparable measurements across laboratories.

1 **Multiparameter characterisation of a nano-polypropylene**
2 **representative test material with fractionation, light scattering,**
3 **high-resolution microscopy, spectroscopy, and spectrometry**
4 **methods**

5
6 Dorota Bartczak¹, Aneta Sikora¹, Heidi Goenaga-Infante¹, Korinna Altmann², Roland
7 Drexel³, Florian Meier³, Enrica Alasonati⁴, Marc Lelong⁴, Florence Cado⁴, Carine Chivas-
8 Joly⁴, Marta Fadda⁵, Alessio Sacco⁵, Andrea Mario Rossi⁵, Daniel Pröfrock⁶, Dominik
9 Wippermann⁶, Francesco Barbero⁷, Ivana Fenoglio⁷, Andy M. Booth⁸, Lisbet Sørensen⁸,
10 Amaia Igartua⁸, Charlotte Wouters⁹, Jan Mast⁹, Marta Barbaresi¹⁰, Francesca Rossi¹¹,
11 Maurizio Piergiovanni¹⁰, Monica Mattarozzi¹⁰, Maria Careri¹⁰, Thierry Caebergs¹², Anne-
12 Sophie Piette¹², Jeremie Parot¹³ and Andrea Mario Giovannozzi^{5, *}

13
14 ¹National Measurement Laboratory, LGC Limited, 10 Priesley Road, Guildford, UG2 7XY, United Kingdom

15 ²Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und – prüfung (BAM), Unter den Eichen 87, Berlin, Germany

16 ³Postnova Analytics GmbH, Rankinestr. 1, 86899 Landsberg a. Lech, Germany

17 ⁴Laboratoire National de Métrologie et d'Essais (LNE), 1 rue Gaston Boissier, 75015 Paris, France

18 ⁵Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (INRiM), Strada delle Cacce 91, 10135 Torino, Italy

19 ⁶Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon, Institute of Coastal Environmental Chemistry, Inorganic Environmental
20 Chemistry, Max-Planck Str. 1, 21502 Geesthacht, Germany

21 ⁷Department of Chemistry, University of Torino, Torino, Italy

22 ⁸SINTEF Ocean, Department of Climate and Environment, Trondheim, Norway

23 ⁹Trace Elements and Nanomaterials, Sciensano, Groeselenberg 99, 1180 Uccle, Belgium

24 ¹⁰University of Parma, Department of Chemistry, Life Sciences and Environmental Sustainability, Parco Area
25 delle Scienze 17/A, 43124 Parma, Italy

26 ¹¹MEM, CNR Institute of Materials for Electronics and Magnetism, Parco Area delle Scienze 37/A, Parma,
27 43124, Italy

28 ¹²FPS Economy, DG Quality and Safety, Metrology Division (SMD), Bd du Roi Albert II, 16 – 1000 Brussels,
29 Belgium

30 ¹³SINTEF Industry, Department of Biotechnology and Nanomedicine, Trondheim, Norway

31
32 ***Corresponding author: a.giovannozzi@inrim.it**

37 **Abstract:** Reference and quality control materials with comparable physicochemical properties to
38 nanoplastic contaminants present in environmental and food nanoplastics are currently lacking. Here
39 we report a nanoplastic polypropylene material prepared using a top-down approach involving
40 mechanical fragmentation of larger plastics. The material was found to be homogeneous and stable
41 in suspension and has been characterised for average particle size, size distribution range, particle
42 number concentration, polypropylene mass fraction and inorganic impurity content using a wide
43 range of analytical methods, including AF4, cFFF, PTA, (MA)DLS, MALS, SEM, AFM, TEM, STEM,
44 EDS, Raman, ICP-MS and pyGC-MS. The material was found to have a broad size distribution,
45 ranging from 50 nm to over 200 nm, with the average particle size value dependent on the technique
46 used to determine it. Particle number concentration ranged from 1.7 - 2.4 E10 g⁻¹, according to PTA.
47 Spectroscopy techniques confirmed the material was polypropylene, with evidence of aging due to
48 an increased level of oxidation. Measured mass fraction was found to depend on the marker used
49 and ranged between 3 - 5 µg g⁻¹. Inorganic impurities such as Si, Al, Mg, K, Na, S, Fe, Cl and Ca
50 were also identified at ng g⁻¹ levels. Comparability and complementarity across the measurement
51 methods and techniques is also discussed.

52

53 Keywords: nanoplastic, particle size, number concentration, polypropylene identification,
54 polypropylene mass fraction

55

56 1. Introduction

57 Over 350 million tons of plastic waste are produced globally every year, of which nearly two-thirds
58 are estimated to be released into the environment as plastic waste [1]. Numerous international
59 organisations, including the United Nations (UN), World Health Organization (WHO), and
60 Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) have called for actions to
61 increase our understanding and to propose effective mitigation measures to protect the public and
62 the environment from plastic pollution. In Europe, the European Commission (EC) has responded
63 through policy documents, including the Green Deal and the EU Plastics Strategy. The EC has also
64 advanced legislation, including the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of
65 Chemicals (REACH) and the Drinking Water Directive (DWD, 2020/2184 [2]). In the United Kingdom,
66 the Government has set a target of eliminating avoidable plastic waste by end of 2042 to prevent
67 further pollution with plastics.

68 Despite joint international efforts to reduce the amount of plastic waste, it continues to be released
69 into the environment at an unprecedented scale [3]. Once in the environment, plastics undergo
70 fragmentation upon exposure to UV radiation and through mechanical stress [4]. Larger pieces of
71 plastic are fragmented into microplastics (MP), defined as particles in the size range from 1 μm to 1
72 mm [5] or 5 mm [6], and eventually to nanoplastics (NP), with sizes below 1000 nm [7]. MP and NP
73 have been reported in all environmental compartments, accumulating in soils and sediments, and
74 considered critical persistent pollutants of an increasing global concern owing to their high durability
75 and long-life [8].

76 The potential long-term impacts on biota and human health arising from MPs and NPs present in the
77 environment are still unknown, and there are no defined maximum daily exposure limits due to the
78 lack of robust toxicological data [9]. This is, in part, due to the absence of metrologically validated,
79 harmonised and standardised measurement methods, as well as the lack of consensus with regards
80 to the typical quantities (per size class, especially for particles with sizes below 1000 nm) and
81 physicochemical characteristics of various types of plastics typically occurring in the environment.
82 There remains a need to develop robust analytical methods for plastic characterisation, especially
83 at the sub-micron and nanoscale.

84 The characterisation and quantification of plastic particles <1000 nm is challenging due to their
85 multimodal and polydisperse character and irregular shape, but also due to the limitations of
86 analytical techniques routinely used for the characterisation of other types of particles in the size
87 range from 1 – 1000 nm. For instance, commonly used light scattering techniques, such as dynamic
88 light scattering ('DLS' or Multi-Angle DLS 'MADLS' [10]), multi-angle static light scattering (MALS
89 [11]) or Particle Tracking Analysis (PTA [12]), as well as high-resolution microscopy methods, such
90 as transmission electron microscopy (TEM [13]), Scanning electron microscopy (SEM [14]) or atomic
91 force microscopy (AFM [15]) are compatible with particles in that size range, but they cannot easily
92 distinguish between plastic particles and other types of particles that might also be present in the
93 sample [16]. Conversely, spectrometry-based methods, such as pyrolysis gas chromatography mass
94 spectrometry (pyGC-MS), can distinguish plastic particles but do not provide information about
95 particle size or morphology [16]. Moreover, most of the imaging spectroscopy methods, such as
96 micro-Raman (μRaman) or micro-Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (μFTIR), have size
97 detection limits >1000 nm and are therefore unable to characterise and quantify particles in the
98 nanoscale [17].

99 These limitations with individual techniques highlights the need for the development of alternative
100 multi-technique, hyphenated (e.g. multidetector Field-Flow Fractionation 'FFF' [16]) or hybrid
101 approaches (e.g. SEM/RAMAN [18], Dielectrophoresis (DEP)-Raman [19, 20]) involving a
102 combination of measurement methods, allowing simultaneous characterisation of multiple
103 parameters at the nanoscale, including chemical identity, particle size, size distribution, as well as

104 mass and number concentration. Such combined approaches will be invaluable in supporting
105 policymakers, international standardisation efforts and testing laboratories, and will enable the
106 development and characterisation of future NP quality control (QC) measures and reference
107 materials (RMs), which are currently unavailable.

108 This work describes a systematic evaluation of the applicability of selected light scattering,
109 fractionation, high-resolution microscopy, spectroscopy and spectrometry methods, as standalone
110 techniques and in combination (including hyphenated and hybrid), for characterising plastic particles
111 <1000 nm. Assessment was conducted using a combination of commercially available polystyrene
112 (PS) microspheres and more environmentally relevant polypropylene (PP) nanoplastic particles
113 produced through a top-down method. The complementarity and comparability of the different
114 analysis techniques are discussed, including when applied in combination, along with main sources
115 of measurement errors for selected techniques and measurands.

116

117 **2. Experimental Section**

118 **2.1 Materials**

119 **2.1.1 Monodispersed polystyrene spheres**

120 A single batch of PS microspheres of approximately 200 nm (202 ± 4 nm), $k=2$ (Duke 3200A) was
121 purchased from Thermo Fisher (Fremont, CA) to use as a quality control material (QC). The material
122 was characterised by the manufacturer for size using TEM and was supplied with indicative
123 information on the solid content. In addition, 60 nm PS beads with a certified size ($60 \text{ nm} \pm 4 \text{ nm}$,
124 Nanosphere™ Size Standard 3060A) were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA,
125 USA).

126

127 **2.1.2 Polydispersed polypropylene particles**

128 A polydispersed nanoPP test material containing particles <1000 nm in size was produced by
129 fragmenting PP pellets with an UltraTurrax and subsequently applying filtration (Figure 1).
130 Approximately 25 g of PP pellets were placed into a glass beaker containing 250 mL acetone. The
131 beaker was cooled on ice for ~30 min, after which the suspension was filtered through a pleated filter
132 to remove larger particles. The volume of the resulting filtrate was then reduced to 10% (ca. 25 mL)
133 by rotary evaporation and diluted with ultrapure water. The suspension was subjected to rotary
134 evaporation again to remove the remaining acetone (~30 min at 100 mbar). The resulting aqueous
135 suspension was filtered again. The final filtrate was divided into 890 brown glass vials, each
136 containing ~2 mL of PP suspension.

137 The homogeneity of the nanoPP material was investigated by analysing the content of 12 different
138 bottles in duplicate by PTA to determine particle size and number concentration (as described in
139 Section 2.2). Material stability was tested periodically using batch DLS analysis (as described in
140 Section 2.2) at time 0, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months, covering the period over which all
141 measurements described in the work reported here were performed. Three bottles were measured
142 in duplicate at each time point. All materials were diluted, as required by each technique, in ultrapure
143 water ($18.2 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}$, $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, Elga Purelab Chorus, Viola Water Technologies, Buckinghamshire, UK)
144 prior to analysis, unless stated otherwise.

145
146
147
148

Figure 1: Fragmentation of PP pellets with UltraTurrax (left), filtration of fragmented PP for fractionation (centre) and the final bottled PP suspension (right).

149

2.2 Instruments and Methods

150

2.2.1 PTA

151

152

153

154

155

156

157

158

159

160

161

162

163

164

165

166

167

168

169

A NanoSight NS300 (PTA; Malvern Panalytical Ltd., UK) system equipped with a laser module with a wavelength at 405 nm, high sensitivity scientific complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (sCMOS) camera, a syringe pump and Low-Volume-Flow-Cell (LVFC), was used by Postnova Analytix and LGC. UNITO used a ZetaView® PMX-120 PTA (Particle Metrix GmbH, Germany), equipped with a light source wavelength of 488 nm and a 90° laser scattering video microscope with 10× magnification. The instruments were switched on 30 min prior to measurement. The flow-through cells were cleaned with ultrapure water before each new sample injection, as well as between individual aliquots of the same sample and at the end of all measurements, until no more particles are detected. For the NanoSight NS300, each sample was diluted gravimetrically ~100 x in ultrapure water to a final particle number concentration of approximately 20-100 particles per frame and shaken manually prior to analysis. Measurements were performed in a flow mode, and the camera settings and focus were optimised manually. All measurements were conducted at room temperature, allowing the instruments to automatically determine the actual temperature in the flow cell and assign an associated water viscosity value for data analysis. Captures with a duration of 60 s were recorded and repeated 5 times per sample. For analysis by PMX-120, each sample was diluted ~700 times (gravimetrically). The sensitivity and shutter were set to 80 and 100, respectively, with a frame rate of 30 fps and a minimum track length of 15 frames. For each sample, 3 sets of 33 videos (1 second each) were recorded, analysing a minimum of ~ 2500 NPs per measurement.

170

2.2.2 DLS (MADLS)

171

172

173

174

175

176

177

178

179

A MADLS Zetasizer Ultra instrument (Malvern Panalytica, UK) equipped with 173°, 90° and 13° angles and a low-volume, high-performance black Quartz Cuvette (ZEN 2112) was used by LGC and INRIM. The MADLS instruments were switched on at least 30 mins prior to analysis. At LGC, the sample was analysed both undiluted and following an ~10x dilution in ultrapure water. Individual samples were measured 3-5 times under the following repeatability conditions: analysis temperature 25 °C, with media viscosity set to 0.8872 mPa.s and the refractive index (RI) set to 1.33, while the material RI was set to 1.49 and the absorbance set to 0.01. Multiple narrow peak mode was used. At INRIM, 5 runs per measurement were conducted on each undiluted sample. The operating temperature was maintained at 25 °C. The average hydrodynamic diameter (z-average) and

180 polydispersity index (PDI) were obtained from the correlation function fitted according to ISO
181 22412:2017.

182

183 **2.2.3 FFF-MALS**

184 At Hereon, centrifugal FFF (cFFF) measurements were performed using a CF2000 system
185 (Postnova Analytics, Landsberg a. L., Germany) equipped with an autosampler, a degasser unit and
186 a UVD disinfection unit. The system was equipped with an analytical fractionation channel with a
187 thickness of 231 μm , a channel area of 100 cm^2 and a void volume of 2 mL. A typical injection volume
188 of 20 μL was used for the measurements. The method employed a start speed of 3500 rpm and
189 maintained a flow rate of 1.5 mL/min. The injection time was set to 38 seconds, followed by a
190 relaxation time of 5 min. The carrier liquid was 0.2% (v/v) NovaChem100. The cFFF system was
191 connected to a MALS detector (PN3621). After each run, a rinse step of 10 min was conducted to
192 overcome potential carry over effects and ensure reproducible conditions for subsequent
193 measurements. At the end of measuring each batch of samples, a blank run was performed injecting
194 only MilliQ. In total, 3 samples with 4 replicates each were fractionated and characterised. Samples
195 were diluted five-fold in MilliQ prior to analysis. Evaluation of the data obtained from the MALS
196 detector was conducted by applying a sphere model to the scattering data. Typically, the range of
197 12° to 156° was used for data evaluation, where 68° and 132° were excluded from evaluation as
198 these angles did not provide sufficient data owing to the detectors needing to be replaced.

199

200 At Postnova Analytics, multi-detector (MD)-AF4 experiments were performed on a AF2000 MT
201 system (Postnova Analytics, Landsberg a. L., Germany). An analytical AF4 channel with a tip-to-tip
202 length of 277 mm, a width of 20 mm and hip width of 5 mm was equipped with a regenerated cellulose
203 membrane (RC) with a molecular cut-off of 10 kDa and a 350 μm spacer height. The temperature
204 during fractionation was kept constant at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$ using a channel thermostat. The samples were
205 injected using an autosampler. The fractionation system was directly coupled to a UV/Vis detector
206 and a MALS detector (21 active angles, laser wavelength 532 nm). The UV absorbance was
207 measured at 254 nm. The MALS detector was normalised using fractionated 60 nm PS beads and
208 a spherical fit model. A volume of 20 μL of a 40 ppb PS bead suspension was injected as received,
209 with no sample preparation performed. The carrier liquid consisted of 0.2% (v/v) NovaChem100
210 (PN). For the fractionation, a detector flow rate of 0.50 mL/min, an injection flow rate of 0.20 mL/min
211 and an injection time of 5 min was applied. The initial cross flow rate was set to 1.20 mL/min. After
212 a transition time of 0.2 min, the cross-flow rate was kept constant for 0.2 min and then decreased
213 within 40 min using a power decay (exponent = 0.2) to 0.10 mL/min. This last cross flow rate was
214 kept for 10 min, followed by a rinse step of 5 min. All measurements were conducted in duplicate. In
215 total, 12 vials (each with 2 aliquots) were fractionated and characterised. MALS data evaluation was
216 performed within an angular range of 12° to 156° , the scattering intensities were evaluated by fitting
217 a sphere model to the angular dependent scattering data to obtain size information (radius of
218 gyration, R_g). This type of fit model yielded results with low deviations across the complete size range
219 with squared correlation coefficients above 0.98. The sphere model represented the data points
220 accurately around the peak maximum. Slight deviations for the smallest and largest size fractions
221 were observed, but comparable results were derived from a fourth order polynomial fit. The system
222 was controlled by the NovaFFF Software (version 2.2.0.1) and the data evaluation was performed
223 in the NovaAnalysis software (version 2408).

224 At LNE, MD-AF4 analysis was performed on an AF4 system (AF2000 Postnova Analytics) coupled
225 to MALS (DAWN HELEOS II, Wyatt Technology) equipped with 18 angles and UV (SPD-20A,
226 Shimadzu) detectors. A metal-free analytical AF4 channel (tip-to-tip length of 277 mm, 20 mm width
227 and 5 mm hip width) (Postnova Analytics) was used. The carrier liquid was prepared by dissolving
228 Novachem100 (Postnova Analytics) in ASTM Type I ultrapure water to a final concentration of

229 0.0125% (v/v) and passing through a 0.1 μm filter (RC, Postnova Analytics). The channel out-let flow
230 rate was 0.5 mL/min. MALS data treatment was performed using the Berry model of second degree,
231 11 angles and the Astra Software (version 6.1.7, Wyatt Technology). The UV detector was used for
232 MALS data treatment and for recovery calculation. The uncertainty associated with the R_g was
233 established as the combination of the repeatability, the average MALS model uncertainty and the
234 size bias between the certified value and the measured value of a 200 nm PS standard. Blanks
235 consisting of pure carrier liquid were injected between samples and no carry over was observed.
236 Aliquots of the nanoPP suspension were characterised without any dilution or further sample
237 treatment (e.g. filtration or ultrasonication).

238 At SMD, MD-AF4 analysis was performed on a Wyatt Eclipse DualTec, equipped with a UV/Vis
239 detector (Agilent G7114A), a MALS detector (DAWN HELEOS II, Wyatt Technology), and an inline
240 Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Panalytical, UK). The carrier was SDS (0.01% m/v) in ultrapure
241 water, filtered through a 0.1 μm filter (RC, Millipore). The separation method was an isocratic
242 program for most of its duration and separation. The UV/Vis wavelength was set to 200 nm, and
243 blank subtraction applied.

244

245 **2.2.4 TEM and STEM-EDX**

246 At Sciensano, conventional TEM imaging was performed using a Tecnai G2 Spirit 12 (120 kV,
247 Thermo Fisher Scientific, Eindhoven, The Netherlands) with BioTwin lens configuration equipped
248 with a 4X4K Eagle CCD camera and using TIA software (Thermo Fisher Scientific). In addition, a
249 Talos F200S G2 (200kV, Thermo Fisher Scientific) equipped with a Ceta 16M camera, high angle
250 annular dark field (HAADF) detector, Super-X detector and Velox software (Version 3.8, Thermo
251 Fisher Scientific) was used for scanning TEM coupled with energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy
252 (STEM-EDX) to perform chemical mapping. The 200 nm PS QC material was diluted 10 times using
253 MilliQ water and deposited on Alcian blue pre-treated pioloform- and carbon-coated copper grids
254 (Agar Scientific, Essex, England) by grid-on-drop deposition (10' contact) [21]. The size properties
255 of the particles were measured semi-automatically from TEM images using the ParticleSizer plugin
256 [22] in the ImageJ software. The total measurement uncertainty was determined by a validation
257 study, following an approach similar to Verleysen et al. [23], consisting of three replicate
258 measurements per day for 5 consecutive days and measuring at least 500 particles per
259 measurement (see detailed methodology in Electronic Supplementary Information, section E). The
260 nanoPP suspension was used undiluted and different methods for the TEM grid preparation were
261 tested: untreated, Alcian blue pre-treated and glow discharged pioloform- and carbon-coated copper
262 grids (Agar Scientific, Essex, England). Sample deposition on the grid was done by either grid-on-
263 drop deposition (10' contact), drop-on-grid deposition followed by evaporation drying [21] (overnight),
264 or on-grid ultracentrifugation. Size properties of particles were measured manually from TEM images
265 in ImageJ.

266 At the University of Parma, TEM analysis was performed using a JEOL JEM-2200FS field-emission
267 microscope equipped with an EDX detector (Oxford Xplore), operated at an acceleration voltage of
268 200 kV [24, 25]. Ultra-thin carbon-coated copper grids (200 mesh, Electron Microscopy Society)
269 were selected to provide optimal support. The images were recorded in both TEM imaging mode
270 using a Gatan UltraScan US1000 camera and in STEM imaging mode using a HAADF detector. For
271 each grid, 20 micrographs were acquired in random sampling mode, ensuring coverage of both the
272 border and centre regions of the grid. Ultrapure water blanks were analysed to detect any potential
273 contamination introduced during sample preparation and handling. Particle counting and sizing were
274 performed using the open-source ImageJ software. The intensity range was adjusted to isolate
275 particles from the background. To improve particle separation and minimise noise, manual
276 thresholding and morphological filtering were applied. Sample preparation was performed in a

277 cleanroom (ISO level 6) to minimise cross-contamination. Glassware was pre-cleaned according to
278 the internal standard operating procedure developed within the PlasticTrace project, involving a
279 sequential washing and sonication for at least 5 minutes using TritonX-100 (0.1 mg/L), acetone and
280 an isopropanol/water solution (20% v/v). A suspension of the 200 nm PS QC material was diluted in
281 ultrapure water to a final concentration of 0.04 mg/mL. A 20 μ L aliquot of the suspension was then
282 drop-cast on the TEM grid and dried at room temperature. Three different sample preparation
283 protocols were tested using nanoPP suspensions at a nominal concentration of 0.04 mg/mL. (i) Drop-
284 Casting: an aliquot of 100 μ L of the nanoPP suspension was dried in a clean vial at 50 °C,
285 reconstituted with 30 μ L of ultrapure water, dried again, and reconstituted with an additional 10 μ L
286 of ultrapure water. The final suspension was then drop-cast on the TEM grid and dried at room
287 temperature. (ii) Concentration by heating bath: 100 μ L of the nanoPP suspension was placed
288 directly into a vial containing the TEM grid and dried at 50 °C using a hot bath. Subsequently, the
289 sample was reconstituted with 30 μ L of ultrapure water directly over the grid and dried again. (iii)
290 Concentration by SpeedVac, drying and drop-casting: 2 mL of the nanoPP suspension was dried at
291 50 °C using a SpeedVac system. The sample was reconstituted with 30 μ L of ultrapure water, dried
292 again, and reconstituted with an additional 10 μ L of ultrapure water. The final suspension was then
293 drop-cast on a TEM grid and dried at room temperature.

294

295 **2.2.5 SEM**

296 SEM analysis was conducted using a Zeiss Ultra-plus SEM with a field emission source and a Gemini
297 column. The in-lens detector measured secondary electrons at 3 kV at a 3.0 mm working distance.
298 A charge compensator system was used to blow nitrogen gas near the samples and neutralise
299 negative charges. Samples were prepared using conventional evaporation deposition, where an
300 aliquot of the nanoPP suspension was placed directly onto silicon support. For each sample, three
301 series of 300 particles were counted and measured using the Platypus software developed by Pollen
302 Metrology [26], allowing the type-A uncertainty related to repeatability of the SEM measurements to
303 be determined. The estimation of the statistic law parameters that best fitted the SEM data for each
304 sample was carried out using R-Studio software with a program developed by the LNE statistics
305 team [27]. The size distributions measured by EM-based analysis were fitted by a log-normal
306 function. The output mean diameter ($d_{eq. mean}$) and standard deviation (s) were determined,
307 associated with the 95%-confidence interval for both parameters. were determined, associated with
308 the 95%-confidence interval for both parameters. were determined, associated with the 95%-
309 confidence interval for both parameters. were determined, associated with the 95%-confidence
310 interval for both parameters. were determined, associated with the 95%-confidence interval for both
311 parameters. were determined, associated with the 95%-confidence interval for both parameters.

312

313 **2.2.6 AFM**

314 AFM measurements were performed with an Asylum Research MFP-3D Infinity instrument, operated
315 in intermittent contact mode. Olympus AC160 and Nanosensors PPP-NCHR tips were selected
316 depending on the substrate and to optimise the imaging. The instrument was calibrated against step
317 height topography standards for Z-scale (height) measurements, which are the most accurate as
318 they are less affected by the tip convolution effect compared to lateral size measurements.

319

320 **2.2.7 DEP-RAMAN and SEM/RAMAN**

321 At INRiM, Raman spectra of 10 vials of nanoPP were acquired by coupling DEP and Raman
322 spectroscopy. A 50 μ L aliquot of each suspension was mixed with 5 μ L of 10 % PBS solution, after
323 which, a 5 μ L aliquot was injected into a home-made DEP cell. The electrical field in the DEP cell
324 was induced by a sinusoidal voltage of 5 V peak-to-peak at a frequency of 1 MHz obtained by a
325 Hewlett-Packard 33120a (United States) function generator. This resulted in negative DEP and net

326 forces on the samples directed towards the centre of the cell, where the confocal volume of a Raman
327 Imaging microscope (DXRxi, Thermo Scientific, United States) was located. The accumulation time
328 before Raman spectra acquisition was 30 s. Spectra were acquired with a 60× water immersion
329 objective (N.A. = 1.1) using an excitation wavelength at 532 nm, a laser power of 20 mW, an
330 exposure time of 1 s for 60 scans (1 minute total per spectrum), and a spectrograph confocal pinhole
331 aperture of 50 μm in diameter. The dispersive Raman system has 5 cm⁻¹ spectral resolution and a
332 spectral range of 500-3100 cm⁻¹.

333 At LNE, a drop of the nanoPP suspension was deposited on a silicon wafer and identified by using
334 μRaman (LabRAM Soleil™ Confocal Raman Microscope) equipped with LabSpec 6 software. The
335 Raman spectral acquisition parameters were set as 532 nm was used with 50% of laser power, a
336 200 μm hole size and 600 lines/mm (500 nm). The exposure time was set at 1 s and accumulation
337 was set to 10 times. The 100× objective was used, and spectra were measured in the spectral range
338 500–3500 cm⁻¹. The spectra were compared with the IDFinder spectral library for the identification
339 of detected particles.

340

341 **2.2.8 pyGC-MS**

342 Six replicate aqueous nanoPP suspension samples were individually homogenised by gentle
343 shaking followed by 250 μL from each bottle being sub-sampled into pyrolysis cups for quantification.
344 MilliQ water was used as blank samples. The water was removed by gentle evaporation prior to
345 analysis. Pyrolysis gas chromatography – mass spectrometry (PyGC-MS) was performed using a
346 Frontier Multi-Shot Pyrolyzer (PY-3030D) coupled to an Agilent 7890A GC with an Agilent 5975C
347 MS (Py-GC/MS) (Santa Clara, CA, USA). The pyrolyzer was operated in single-shot mode with
348 pyrolysis at 600 °C (1.0 min). The pyrolyzer interface and GC inlet temperatures were 320 °C, and
349 the split ratio was 25:1. The carrier gas was helium at a constant flow of 1 mL/min. Separation was
350 achieved using a Frontier Ultra ALLOY+-5 capillary column (30 m length, 0.25 μm film thickness,
351 and 0.25 mm internal diameter). The column oven temperature was programmed at 40 °C (2 min)
352 and ramped up by 20 °C/min until it reached 320 °C (25 min hold). The transfer line temperature was
353 320 °C, the ion source temperature was 230 °C, and the quadrupole temperature was 150 °C. The
354 ion source was operated in SIM mode using several established target peaks for quantification of
355 PP: 2,4-dimethylhept-1-ene using marker ions m/z 70 and 126; 2,4,6-trimethyl-1-nonene (meso) and
356 2,4,6-trimethyl-1-nonene (racemic) using marker ions m/z 69 and 97; 2,4,6,8-tetramethyl-1-
357 undecene (isotactic), 2,4,6,8-tetramethyl-1-undecene (heterotactic) and 2,4,6,8-tetramethyl-1-
358 undecene (syntactic) using marker ions m/z 69 and 111. External calibration curves were prepared
359 from an in-house standard PP reference material by complete solvent dissolution and subsequent
360 dilution to different concentrations. For calibration, a standard PP powder (PP Co-polymer
361 CRT201.00 from CARAT GmbH, <100 μm) was dissolved in xylene (130 °C, 30 min followed by
362 ultrasonication in a sonication bath, 10 min 80 °C), diluted and spiked in resulting masses of 0.25-5
363 μg in stainless steel pyrolysis cups. Samples were run in randomised order, with triplicate calibration
364 samples run throughout the series, also in randomised order.

365

366 **2.2.9 ICP-MS/MS and AF4/MALS/ICP-MS**

367 At Hereon, triplicate samples of 50 μL (n=2) and 500 μL (n=1) were digested using 5 mL HNO₃, 2
368 mL HCl and 1 mL HBF₄. Samples were digested at 220°C and 48 bar using microwave assisted acid
369 digestion (BLADE microwave, CEM Corp., Kamp Lintfort, Germany). TFM digestion vessels were
370 pre-cleaned using an ETC EVO II (ANALAB, Hoenheim, France) acid vapor cleaner with HNO₃ (65%
371 w/w) and type I reagent grade water. Digested samples were quantitatively transferred to 50 mL
372 graduated, PP vessels (DigiTUBE®; SCP Science, Quebec, Canada) precleaned with HNO₃ (2%
373 w/w) and filled to a total volume of 50 mL with type I reagent grade water. Sample digests were
374 measured using an ICP-MS/MS (Agilent 8800, Agilent Technologies, Santa Barbara CA, USA)

375 coupled to a prepFAST M5 system (Elemental Scientific, Omaha, Nebraska, USA). A special inert
376 sample introduction kit (AHF analysentechnik AG, Tübingen, Germany) was used to minimise the
377 responses in the blank samples. H₂ and N₂O were employed as reaction gases in MS/MS mode for
378 the quantified elements. Quantified mass-to-charge ratios and corresponding cell modes were
379 selected based on achieved sensitivity, as well as by non-occurrence of isobaric and polyatomic
380 interferences. The instrument was tuned daily to obtain optimal measuring conditions using a tune
381 solution containing Li, Co, Y, Ce and Tl (10 µg L⁻¹). External calibration covering a concentration
382 range from 0 µg L⁻¹ to 10,000 µg L⁻¹ for Si, P, Mg, Al, K, Ca, Ti and Mn automatically diluted by the
383 prepFAST M5 system from two stock solutions (500 µg L⁻¹ and 10,000 µg L⁻¹), as well as online
384 dosed internal standards (10 µg L⁻¹ Rh and Ir) were used for quantification. Potential carry-over
385 effects were monitored by measuring wash blanks (2% HNO₃ (w/w)) after each triplicate of samples.
386 Calibration solutions were freshly prepared immediately before measurement.

387 At Postnova, AF4/MALS/ICP-MS measurements were performed using an AF4 system, as
388 described under 2.2.3, that was hyphenated to an ICP-MS (7900 ICP-MS, Agilent Technologies Inc.
389 USA). The hyphenation was realised using an ICP-MS module (PN 9040), which connected the
390 MALS detector outlet with a T-piece connected to the ICP-MS. Sample introduction on the ICP-MS
391 system consisted of a MicroMist nebuliser and a concentric Scott spray chamber. A plasma gas flow
392 rate of 15 L/min and a nebuliser gas flow rate of 1.05 L/min were applied. All measurements were
393 conducted at a maximum radio frequency power of 1550 W. A collision gas of 4.5 mL/min of Helium
394 was introduced into the collision cell to remove potential polyatomic interferences. The ICP-MS
395 performance was checked and tuned prior to the measurements. The isotopes ²⁴Al, ²⁷Al, ²⁸Si,
396 ³¹P, ³⁵Cl, ³⁸Ca, ⁴⁷Ti, ⁵²Cr, ⁵⁶Fe, ⁶⁰Ni, ⁶³Cu, ⁶⁶Zn, ⁷⁹Br, ⁹⁰Zr were monitored with an integration
397 time of 0.1 s. The carrier liquid consisted of 0.0125% (v/v) NovaChem100 and the same fractionation
398 method was used as described under 2.2.3. The injection volume was increased to 100 µL. A 200
399 nm PS bead with a maximum injection amount of 4 µg was used as a control.

401 **3. Results and Discussion**

402 **3.1 Homogeneity and stability**

403 Homogeneity and stability were assessed only for the nanoPP material prepared as part of the work
404 described here, since the PS material is a commercially available product and as such is considered
405 sufficiently homogeneous and stable.

406 PTA technique was chosen for the purpose of nanoPP material's homogeneity assessment as it
407 allows determination of hydrodynamic size and particle number concentration independent from
408 each other, which are considered critical measurands for particles at the sub-micron and nanoscale.
409 For particle size, the modal particle size was evaluated. The size was less variable than particle
410 number concentration, with no clear outliers detected for either of the two measurands. For the
411 modal particle size, uncertainty associated with homogeneity was around 4.4%. In case of particle
412 number concentration, this value was around 14.4%.

413 Material's stability was tested using DLS, since this light technique is more sensitive to the presence
414 of agglomerates/aggregates (a strong indicator of particle instability) than number-based methods
415 such as PTA. DLS provides information on particle size and size distribution. No significant
416 differences in particle size and particle size distribution were observed over a 6-month period.

417 **3.2 Characterisation of nanoPP**

418 **3.2.1. Particle size and size distribution**

419 Particle size and size distribution of nanoPP was measured in solution with number-based
420 instrumentation (PTA), ensemble intensity-based instrumentation (DLS and MADLS) and ensemble
421 size-resolved instrumentation (MD-AF4), as well as following deposition on solid supports (SEM,
422

423 AFM and TEM). Results from the PTA analyses are presented in Figure 2 and Table 1 as average
 424 mean size values with associated standard deviation. In addition, LGC also calculated the associated
 425 measurement uncertainty.

426
 427 **Figure 2.** Average size distribution graphs obtained with PTA using NanoSight NS300 (black line) and PMX-
 428 120 (red line).

429
 430

Table 1. Particle mean size obtained with PTA.

Institute	Instrument	nanoPP particle mean size (nm)		
		Average (nm)	Stdev (nm)	RSD (%)
LGC	NanoSight NS300	148.1 (n=45)	5.5 (n=45)	4.0
Postnova	NanoSight NS300	147.0 (n=24)	3.5 (n=24)	2.4
UNITO	PMX-120	170.4 (n=15)	4.4 (n=15)	2.6

431
 432
 433 As can be seen in Figure 2 (black line), the size distribution of the particles in the nanoPP material
 434 determined by the NanoSight NS300 instruments suggests a polydisperse distribution with multiple
 435 modes and broad size distribution tailing towards larger sizes. This is consistent with a material
 436 produced via a top-down approach using mechanical fragmentation and sieving to increase the
 437 environmental relevance. The size distribution for the PMX-120 instrument (red line) is shifted
 438 towards larger sizes, which might be related to effects arising from the data processing algorithms
 439 the two different instruments use. Due to the multimodal and polydispersed character of the nanoPP
 440 material, the mean particle size rather than the modal particle size is considered the most appropriate
 441 and more practical measurand for the purpose of comparison with intensity-based methods (like
 442 DLS) described in the following sections. Even in this case, the mean particle size value measured
 443 by the PMX-120 instrument is slightly larger (170.4 nm) than the values determined by the NanoSight
 444 NS300 instruments (147.1 and 148.0 nm). However, if expanded measurement uncertainty (k=2),
 445 calculated as being ~10-11% according to Eurachem/CITAC guidelines, is considered for the
 446 purpose of data comparison, the results obtained by across all three instruments are in agreement
 447 within the associated measurement uncertainty. Measurement repeatability was identified as being
 448 the main factor (~50% of the uncertainty budget) contributing to the overall uncertainty, as expected
 449 for a polydisperse material. The size obtained for the PS QC material was 201.4 ± 2.9 nm (LGC),

450 195.4 ± 2.2 nm (Postnova) and 204.4 ± 1.5 nm (UNITO), in agreement with the size value reported
451 by the manufacturer (202 ± 4.0 nm) and consistent across all experimental set-ups tested.

452 The particle size and size distribution of the nanoPP suspension was also measured with MADLS
453 by LGC and batch DLS by INRIM. The results are presented in Table 2 as average mean size values
454 (MADLS) or average hydrodynamic diameter (z-average; DLS), with associated standard deviation
455 of n measurements. Mean particle size was similar for both DLS (174.9 ± 0.4 nm) and MADLS (186.0
456 ± 3.9 nm), with the slight difference between the two values suggested to be a result of data
457 processing algorithms, being the cumulants method in case of DLS and the distribution algorithm, or
458 so called 'Multiple Narrow Mode', for MADLS. The cumulants model assumes a single particle
459 population, which is represented as a simple Gaussian distribution, with the z-average being the
460 mean size value. In contrast, the distribution algorithm models the correlogram as an intensity
461 contribution for each size band/bin. As such, the cumulants model for a material exhibiting a
462 polydisperse non-Gaussian distribution, as in case of the nanoPP material, might give different
463 results than MADLS. As both DLS and MADLS are intensity-based methods, they are more sensitive
464 to the presence of larger particles than number-based methods such as PTA, which results in the
465 slightly larger mean particle size for the former.

466

467 **Table 2.** Particle mean or z-average size obtained with MADLS and DLS, respectively.

Institute	Particle mean or z-average size (nm)		
	Average (nm)	Stdev (nm)	RSD (%)
LGC (MADLS)	186.0 (n=41)	3.9 (n=41)	2.1
INRIM (DLS)	174.9 (n=15)	0.4 (n=15)	0.2

468

469

470 The results obtained for the different FFF-based methodologies are summarised in Table 3. The
471 AF4-MALS measurements performed by Postnova on the nanoPP suspension showed excellent
472 repeatability, with a mean retention time of 26.7 ± 0.3 min (n=24) (Figure 3). The peak width and
473 peak shape across all investigated aliquots were highly comparable, with insignificant field-off and
474 void peaks. The average MALS 90° signal across all measurements is displayed in black, and the
475 grey area visualises the standard deviation of the MALS 90° signals. Furthermore, as the retention
476 time is directly proportional to the particle hydrodynamic size, the size can be derived using FFF
477 theory. The derived weight-average $R_{g,w}$ of 75 nm ± 1 nm (mean ± stdev, n=48) is equivalent to a
478 sphere with a diameter of 194 nm. The mean particle size derived from angular dependent MALS
479 signal intensities yielded an $R_{g,50}$ = 74 nm ± 1 nm (mean ± stdev, n=48), which is equivalent to a
480 geometrical sphere with a diameter of 191 nm.

481

482

483 **Table 3.** Summary of the size values obtained using the FFF method, with their associated uncertainties (u , $k=1$), and recovery values. Radii of gyration and
 484 hydrodynamic radii, respectively, are displayed as number (Rn), weight (Rw) and z-averages (Rz). Additionally, cumulative radii values at 50% are listed in the table
 485 as R50 values. The physical nature of the radius is specified for each dataset, together with the model used.

Institute	Set-up	Radius/Model	Rn		Rw		Rz		R50		System recovery (%)
			Mean \pm stdev* (nm)	u, k=1 (%)	Mean \pm stdev* (nm)	u, k=1 (%)	Mean \pm stdev* (nm)	u, k=1 (%)	Mean \pm stdev* (nm)	u, k=1 (%)	
Postnova	AF4-MALS 90° Signal	hydrodynamic – Retention theory			103 \pm 2	2			98 \pm 2	2	>75
Postnova	AF4-MALS	gyration - Sphere	46 \pm 4	8	75 \pm 1	1	96 \pm 4	4	74 \pm 1	1	> 75
LNE	AF4-UV-MALS	gyration – Berry2	81 \pm 4	5	86 \pm 4	5	91 \pm 5	6	-	-	~74
SMD	AF4-UV-MALS	gyration - Sphere	64 \pm 10	16	92 \pm 3	3	111 \pm 2	1	-	-	> 70
Hereon	cFFF-MALS	gyration - Sphere	65 \pm 5	8	67 \pm 5	7	69 \pm 5	7	-	-	> 70

*n (number of replicate measurement) is given in the Experimental, Results and/or ESI Sections.

486
487

489

490 **Figure 3.** Average AF4-MALS elution fractogram obtained with 90° angle by Postnova.

491

492 At LNE, six replicates of each nanoPP vial were analysed on two different days to include daily
 493 variability in the measurement precision. The results of the characterisation show excellent
 494 repeatability, weight-average $R_{g,w}$ of $86 \text{ nm} \pm 4 \text{ nm}$ and a recovery of about 74% (Table 3). Similar
 495 results were obtained at SMD, with slightly higher $R_{g,z}$ and $R_{g,w}$ and recoveries higher than 70%
 496 (Table 3 and Electronic Supplementary Information, Section E).

497 Taking in account the different nature of the measurands, the associated uncertainties ($k=1$), and
 498 the different model used for fitting MALS signal intensities, the values measured by the participants
 499 using flow-FFF are in good agreement among them, with FFF theory ($R_{h,w}$ of $103 \pm 2 \text{ nm}$, Table 3)
 500 and PTA, DLS and MADLS results (Tables 1 and 2).

501 Furthermore, at Hereon, four replicates of each nanoPP vial were analysed using cFFF coupled to
 502 MALS (Table 3). $R_{g,z}$ and $R_{g,w}$ values obtained with this instrumental set-up were lower than values
 503 reported for AF4 (see Electronic Supplementary Information, Section F, for details), but closer to
 504 reported PTA values (Table 1). Although the explanation of these inter-instrumental and inter-
 505 detector differences is analytically interesting, it was beyond the scope of this work. In general, MD-
 506 FFF methods produced comparable size characterisation data consistent with PTA, DLS, and
 507 MADLS results. It is also worth noting that FFF channel recoveries of >70% were achieved in all
 508 laboratories and with all systems, meeting method acceptance criteria described in ISO 21362 [28].

509 SEM-EDX was used to obtain size and size distribution data on nanoPP, as well as elemental
 510 information. Representative SEM images shown in Figure 4 reveal that the nanoPP material
 511 comprised particles with irregular shapes and a broad size distribution, ranging from ~50 nm to ~160
 512 nm, and in agreement with size values reported by the number- and intensity-based analysis
 513 techniques. The EDX spectrum of the imaged particle population in the nanoPP sample revealed
 514 clearly visible peaks relating to the oxygen O K α line (Figure 5). The observable S K α signal
 515 potentially comes from the isotactic form of the PP polymer, with cross linkage in the presence of
 516 sulphur [29]. The copper peak Cu L α and the carbon peak C K α come from the substrate (carbon
 517 and pioloform coated Cu grid) used to deposit the particles, whilst the Al K α signal comes from the
 518 sample holder.

519

520
521
522
523

Figure 4: Representative SEM images of particles present in the nano-PP sample with magnification $\times 10\,000$ for image on the left and magnification $\times 100\,000$ for image on the right.

524
525
526
527

Figure 5: EDX spectrum performed on the selection of particles present in the nanoPP sample as indicated on the SEM image (right) and EDX mapping in the same area (left).

528
529
530
531
532
533
534
535
536
537
538
539

STEM-EDX analysis of the nanoPP material, deposited by various methods, revealed the presence of several chemical compounds (mostly salts and other inorganic compounds, see Electronic Supplementary Information, Section F). Grids prepared by grid-on-drop deposition and using Alcian blue grid staining resulted in the least amount of interference of various deposited compounds. From such a grid, a size histogram of area-equivalent circular diameter (ECD) was constructed based on the manual measurement of 74 particles, resulting in a mean ECD of 166 nm (Electronic Supplementary Information, section F, Figure 1), consistent with the results from characterisation techniques able to analyse the particles in suspension. The limited statistics reflect the low particle concentration on the grid. While most particles were isolated, a few agglomerates were also observed, in which case constituent particles that could be resolved visually were measured individually. The composition of a subset of particles was verified by STEM-EDX to be sure that the C signal, indicative of plastic composition, was dominating. However, since C is also present in the

540 supporting film, it cannot be said with certainty that the particles included in the size analysis are
541 nanoPP.

542 Electronic Supplementary Information, Section E, gives an overview on how to validate TEM for
543 reliable determination of particle size and shape based on the 200 nm PS QC material. It
544 demonstrates that accurate and precise measurements can be obtained for monomodal and
545 monodispersed nanoplastic particles, when the particle concentration is sufficiently high. In contrast,
546 attempts to measure the size of nanoPP demonstrates that detection and analysis of environmentally
547 relevant nanoplastics with TEM is much more challenging. Currently, there is no reliable method to
548 selectively separate and enrich nanoplastics with low abundancies to enable analysis in the same
549 way as QC materials. While analytical TEM, such as STEM-EDX, can be useful for detecting false-
550 positive plastic identifications through elemental composition analysis and thus serve as a
551 complementary technique to DLS and PTA, it cannot directly confirm the presence of plastics.
552 Analysis of the nanoPP material STEM-EDX at the University of Parma TEM produced results that
553 were in agreement with those described above (see Electronic Supplementary Information, section
554 G).

555 With (classical) AFM performed at SMD only mechanical measurement was possible. Reliable
556 dimensional measurement was achieved by using deposition method described in the Results
557 section, which yielded a sufficient amount of particles without visible agglomeration. Overall, the size
558 range measured with AFM was in agreement with the size reported by SEM and TEM (see Electronic
559 Supplementary Information, Section H for details).

560

561 3.2.2. Particle number concentration

562 Particle number concentration was measured with PTA by LGC and Postnova (using NS300
563 instruments) and UNITO (using a PMX-120 instrument), with the results presented as average
564 particle number concentrations with associated standard deviation (Table 4). In addition, LGC also
565 calculated the associated measurement uncertainty as being ~19% (k=2, calculated according to
566 Eurachem/CITAC guidelines), with repeatability in particle counting identified as the main
567 contributing factor (~80%). The nanoPP concentrations determined across the 3 instruments range
568 from $1.73^{10} \pm 2.47^9$ to $2.4^{10} \pm 2.6^9$, which are in agreement, considering the associated measurement
569 uncertainty (k=2).

570

571

Table 4. Particle number concentration obtained with PTA.

Institute	Particle number concentration (g ⁻¹)		
	Average (g ⁻¹)	Stdev (g ⁻¹)	RSD (%)
Postnova	1.73 E10 (n=24)	2.47 E9 (n=24)	14.3
LGC	2.04 E10 (n=45)	1.78 E9 (n=45)	8.7
UNITO	2.4 E10 (n=15)	2.6 E9 (n=15)	10.8

572

573

574

574 3.2.3. Chemical identification

575 In Figure 6, Raman spectra are shown for bulk PP (as reference; grey), nanoPP with DEP off (red,
576 background), and nanoPP with DEP on (blue). All nanoPP peak assignments are highlighted and
577 detailed in the Electronic Supplementary Information (Section I), alongside a comparison to the bulk
578 PP. The nanoPP spectrum exhibits most of the characteristic PP peaks; however, differences were
579 observed in peak positions, as well as in their relative intensities and widths. For example, the peak
580 (d) at 2840 cm⁻¹, assigned to the symmetric stretching of CH₂, shifted to 2848 cm⁻¹, suggesting XXX.

581 In addition, two peaks assigned to the stretching of carbonyl groups (C = O) appear at 1650 cm⁻¹
 582 and 1605 cm⁻¹, possibly formed due to oxidation of nanoPP during its preparation procedure, where
 583 the PP granules were soaked in acetone and then dispersed. The fingerprint region also presents
 584 significant variations: the peaks of the bulk PP at 1436 cm⁻¹, 1254 cm⁻¹, 1219 cm⁻¹, 1168 cm⁻¹, 1153
 585 cm⁻¹, and 940 cm⁻¹ are shifted to 1445 cm⁻¹, 1277 cm⁻¹, 1202 cm⁻¹, 1157 cm⁻¹, 1127 cm⁻¹, and 929
 586 cm⁻¹ in nanoPP, respectively. Also, the two evident peaks in bulk PP at 842 cm⁻¹ and 810 cm⁻¹ are
 587 not present in the nanoPP, with the formation of an intermediate peak at 830 cm⁻¹. Despite these
 588 small differences between the spectra of the bulk PP and the nanoPP, the chemical identity of the
 589 nanoPP material was confirmed as polypropylene, with evidence of aging/oxidation having occurred.
 590

591
 592 **Figure 6:** Raman spectra (from bottom to top) of bulk PP, nanoPP with DEP off (background), and nanoPP
 593 with DEP on.
 594

595 Correlative SEM/Raman analysis was also performed on a drop of the nanoPP suspension
 596 deposited on a silicon wafer to assess the global chemistry. As chemical analysis of individual nano-
 597 scale particles by Raman is not possible due to the limited size resolution of this technique in the
 598 nanometer size regime, bulk analysis can be used to generate an average spectrum. The collected
 599 spectra confirmed the material was PP and were in agreement with data obtained by INRiM (see
 600 Electronic Supplementary Information, Section I for details).
 601

602 3.2.4. Polypropylene mass fraction quantification

603 The concentration data for nanoPP determined by pyGC-MS are presented in Table 5. Laboratory
 604 blanks showed a background ranging from 3-30% of the PP, which was not subtracted from the
 605 reported concentrations. The calculated concentration depended on the selected markers. This was
 606 due to the discrepancy in relative peak response of the individual peaks in the duplet and triplet
 607 compounds between the PP reference material and the nanoPP. The racemic 2,4,6-trimethyl-1-
 608 nonene and heterotactic 2,4,6,8-tetramethyl-1-undecene peaks were significantly higher in relative
 609 abundance compared to the reference material (and to what is commonly observed in isotactic PP).
 610 The data generated using these markers are therefore likely to overestimate the nanoPP
 611 concentration in the samples. The concentration of nanoPP would then be in the range 3-5 µg mL⁻¹,
 612 depending on the applied marker. These differences in chemical composition between the PP
 613 reference material and the nanoPP (produced from a different PP source material) highlights a
 614 potential challenge with PP quantification by pyGC-MS. In environmental or human samples the type
 615 of PP present cannot be known and maybe a mixture of different PP particles, meaning the use of a

616 single PP reference material for generating calibration curves could easily over- or underestimate the
617 true PP concentration.

618

619

Table 5. Polypropylene mass fraction obtained with pyGC-MS.

Marker	nanoPP ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)			Blank ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)		
	Average	Stdev	RSD (%)	Average	Stdev	RSD (%)
Sum 2,4,6-Trimethyl-1-nonene	5.0	1.1	22	0.71	0.02	2
Sum 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene	4.3	1.0	24	0.66	0.01	2
2,4-Dimethylhept-1-ene	2.7	0.5	19	0.79	0.01	1
2,4,6-Trimethyl-1-nonene (meso)	3.5	0.7	20	0.75	0.01	1
2,4,6-Trimethyl-1-nonene (race)	9.5	2.1	22	0.73	0.01	1
2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (iso)	2.8	0.6	23	0.74	0.01	1
2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (het)	17	4	22	0.5	0.2	30
2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (syn)	3.7	0.8	22	0.76	0.01	1

620

621

3.2.5. Determination of inorganic impurities

622

623

624

625

626

627

628

629

630

631

632

4. Conclusions

633

634

635

636

637

638

639

640

641

642

643

644

645

5. Authorship contributions

646

647

648

Aneta Sikora: Writing – original draft, review and editing, formal analysis, visualisation, investigation, methodology and validation Dorota Bartczak: Conceptualisation, writing – review and editing, supervision, methodology and validation; Heidi Goenaga-Infante: Writing – review and editing,

649 supervision. Marta Barbaresi: investigation, formal analysis, writing – review and editing. Francesca
650 Rossi: methodology, investigation, formal analysis. Maurizio Piergiovanni: investigation, writing –
651 review and editing. Monica Mattarozzi: writing – review and editing. Maria Careri: writing – review
652 and editing, supervision. Andy M. Booth: data validation, writing – review and editing, Lisbet
653 Sørensen: investigation, methodology, formal analysis, writing. Jeremie Parot: methodology, writing
654 – review and editing, Amaia Igartua: investigation, methodology, formal analysis, writing-review and
655 editing., Thierry Caebergs: investigation, methodology, formal analysis, writing – review and editing,
656 Anne-Sophie Piette: investigation, formal analysis, Roland Drexel: investigation, methodology,
657 formal analysis, validation, writing – review and editing, Florian Meier: validation, writing – review
658 and editing, supervision, Francesco Barbero: writing – review and editing, investigation, formal
659 analysis, visualisation, methodology and validation; Ivana Fenoglio: writing – supervision. Charlotte
660 Wouters: methodology, formal analysis, validation, writing, review and editing. Jan Mast: review and
661 editing, supervision. Enrica Alasonati: investigation, methodology, formal analysis, validation, writing
662 – review and editing; Marta Fadda: investigation, formal analysis, writing – review and editing;
663 Alessio Sacco: investigation, formal analysis, writing – review and editing; Andrea Mario Rossi:
664 supervision, funding; Andrea Mario Giovannozzi: Conceptualisation, writing – review and editing,
665 supervision, methodology, validation and funding.

666 All authors reviewed and approved the final version of manuscript.

667 There are no conflicts to declare.

668

669

6. Acknowledgements

670 - The project 21GRD07 PlasticTrace (Funder ID: <https://doi.org/10.13039/100019599>) has received
671 funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's
672 Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

673 - METROFOOD-IT project has received funding from the European Union -NextGenerationEU,
674 PNRR—Mission 4 “Education and Research” Component 2: from research to business, Investment
675 3.1: Fund for the realisation of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructures—
676 IR0000033 (D.M. Prot. n.120 del 21/06/2022).

677 - Research and innovation network on food and nutrition Sustainability, Safety and Security—Working
678 ON Foods” (ONFOODS) project which received funding from the NRRP and the Mission 4
679 Component 2 Investment 1.3-Call for tender No. 341 of 15/03/2022 of the Italian Ministry of
680 University and Research funded by the European Union-NextGenerationEU. Award Number:
681 Project code PE0000003

682 - This publication has been funded by the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR) in the
683 framework of the continuing-nature project “NEXT- GENERATION METROLOGY”, under the
684 allocation of the Ordinary Fund for research institutions (FOE) 2023 (Ministry Decree n. 789/2023).

685 -

686 7. References

687 [1] Ritchie H. 'How much plastic waste ends up in the ocean?' OurWorldInData.org 2018,
688 '<https://ourworldindata.org/how-much-plastic-waste-ends-up-in-the-ocean>' , last accessed 18/09/25.

689 [2] EU (2020) Directive 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on
690 the quality of water intended for human consumption (recast). Official J EU 23.12.2020.435

691 [3] Pilapitiya, P.N.T. and Ratnayake A.S. 'The world of plastic waste: A review' Cleaner Materials, 2024, 11,
692 p.100220.

693 [4] Andrady, A.L., Barnes, P.W., Bornman, J.F., Gouin, T., Madronich, S., White, C.C., Zepp, R.G. and Jansen,
694 M.A. 'Oxidation and fragmentation of plastics in a changing environment; from UV-radiation to biological
695 degradation'. Science of The Total Environment, 2024, 851, p.158022.

- 696 [5] ISO/TR 21960:2020 'Plastics—environmental aspects—state of knowledge and methodologies'
- 697 [6] Commission Regulation 2023/2055 of 25 September 2023 amending Annex XVII to Regulation (EC) n.
698 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the Registration, Evaluation,
699 Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) as regards synthetic polymer microparticles. Official
700 Journal of the European Union; 2023.
- 701 [7] Gigault, J., Ter Halle, A., Baudrimont, M., Pascal, P.Y., Gauffre, F., Phi, T.L., El Hadri, H., Grassl, B. and
702 Reynaud, S. 'Current opinion: What is a nanoplastic?' *Environmental pollution*, 2018, 235, p.1030-1034.
- 703 [8] Wagner, M., Hartmann, N.B., Verschoor, A., Hüffer, T., Hassellöv, M. and Thompson, R.C. 'Are we speaking
704 the same language? Towards a definition and categorization framework for environmental plastic debris'
705 *Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry, SETAC Europe 28th Annual Meeting*, 2018, p.35.
- 706 [9] Alqahtani S., Alqahtani S., Saquib Q., and Mohiddin F. 'Toxicological impact of microplastics and
707 nanoplastics on humans: understanding the mechanistic aspect of the interaction' *Front Toxicol.* 2023, 5, p.
708 1193386.
- 709 [10] Coones R. T., Kestens V. and Minelli C. 'A comparison of hydrodynamic diameter results from MADLS
710 and DLS measurements for nanoparticle reference materials.' *Journal of Nanoparticle Research* 2025, 27, p.
711 170.
- 712 [11] Zhao, H., Wang, X., Wang, R., Hua, D., Li, K. and Ji, F., Optimal static light scattering detection angle for
713 particulate matter size and concentration measurement. *Measurement Science and Technology*, 2023, 34,
714 p.125802.
- 715 [12] Gallego-Urrea J. A., Tuoriniemi J. and Hassellöv M. 'Applications of particle-tracking analysis to the
716 determination of size distributions and concentrations of nanoparticles in environmental, biological and food
717 samples' *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 2011, 30, p. 473.
- 718 [13] Wouters C., Morales D., Tsilikas K., Verleysen E. and Mast J. 'A validation methodology for size and
719 shape measurement of nanoplastics by transmission electron microscopy' In *BIO Web of Conferences*, EDP
720 Sciences, 2024,129, p. 26039.
- 721 [14] Stine J. S., Aziere N., Harper B. J., and Harper S. L. ' A novel approach for identifying nanoplastics by
722 assessing deformation behavior with scanning electron microscopy' *Micromachines*, 2023, 14, p.1903.
- 723 [15] Galluzzi M., Lancia M., Zheng C., Re V., Castelvetro V., Guo S. and Viaroli S. 'Atomic Force Microscopy
724 (AFM) nanomechanical characterization of micro-and nanoplastics to support environmental investigations in
725 groundwater' *Emerging Contaminants* 2025, 11,p. 100478.
- 726 [16] Huber M. J., Ivleva N.P, Booth A.M., Beer I., Bianchi I., Drexel R., Geiss O. et al. 'Physicochemical
727 characterization and quantification of nanoplastics: applicability, limitations and complementarity of batch and
728 fractionation methods' *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry* 2023, 415, p. 3007.
- 729 [17] Megha S., Unnimaya S., Mithun N., Chidangil S., Kumar S. and Lukose J. 'Raman Spectroscopy Based
730 Approaches for Microplastics Investigations' In *Microplastics in African and Asian Environments: The
731 Influencers, Challenges, and Solutions*, Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, p. 647.
- 732 [18] Gang Li., Yang Z., Pei Z., Li Y., Yang R., Liang Y., Zhang Q. and Jiang G. 'Single-particle analysis of
733 micro/nanoplastics by SEM-Raman technique' *Talanta* 2022, 249, p.123701.
- 734 [19] Fadda M., Sacco A., Altmann K. et al. 'Tracking nanoplastics in drinking water: a new frontier with the
735 combination of dielectrophoresis and Raman spectroscopy' *Micropl. & Nanopl.* 2024, 5, p. 24.
- 736 [20] Placci A., Fadda M., Coralli I., Wang J., Zattoni A., Costa A.L., Portela R., Giovannozzi A.M., Fabbri D.,
737 Melucci D. and Giordani S. 'Multitechnique characterization of eco-corona formation on airborne nanoplastics'
738 *RSC advances.* 2025, 28, p. 30849.
- 739 [21] Mast J. et al., NANoREG D2.10 SOP 01 Preparation of EM-grids containing a representative sample of a
740 dispersed NM, 2018.
- 741 [22] Wagner, T. ParticleSizer. <https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/18649/thorstenwagner/ij-particlesizer>, last
742 accessed on 18/09/2025.

- 743 [23] Verleysen E., Wagner T., Lipinski H.G., Kägi R., Koeber R., Boix-Sanfeliu A., De Temmerman P.J. and
744 Mast J. 'Evaluation of a TEM based Approach for Size Measurement of Particulate (Nano) materials' *Materials*
745 2019, 12, p.2274.
- 746 [24] Piergiovanni M., Mattarozzi M., Verleysen E., Siciliani L., Suman M., Bianchi F., Mast J., Careri M. The
747 Combined ICP-MS, ESEM-EDX, and HAADF-STEM-EDX Approach for the Assessment of Metal Sub-Micro-
748 and Nanoparticles in Wheat Grain. *Molecules* 2024, 29, 3148.
- 749 [25] Riboni N., Ribezzi E., Nasi L., Mattarozzi M., Piergiovanni M., Masino M., Bianchi F., Careri, M.
750 Characterization of Small Micro-and Nanoparticles in Antarctic Snow by Electron Microscopy and Raman
751 Micro-Spectroscopy. *Appl. Sci.* 2024, 14, 1597.
- 752 [26] Foucher, J., Labrosse, A., Dervill'e, A., Zimmermann, Y., Bernard, G., Martinez, S., Gr'onqvist, H.,
753 Baderot, J., Pinzan, F. 'The Coming of Age of the First Hybrid Metrology Software Platform Dedicated to
754 Nanotechnologies (Conference Presentation)' [https://www.spiedigitallibrary.org/conference-proceedings-of-](https://www.spiedigitallibrary.org/conference-proceedings-of-spie/10145/1014507/The-coming-of-age-of-the-first-hybrid-metrology-software/10.1117/12.2258093.short?SSO=1)
755 [spie/10145/1014507/The-coming-of-age-of-the-first-hy](https://www.spiedigitallibrary.org/conference-proceedings-of-spie/10145/1014507/The-coming-of-age-of-the-first-hybrid-metrology-software/10.1117/12.2258093.short?SSO=1)
756 [brid-metrology-](https://www.spiedigitallibrary.org/conference-proceedings-of-spie/10145/1014507/The-coming-of-age-of-the-first-hybrid-metrology-software/10.1117/12.2258093.short?SSO=1)
software/10.1117/12.2258093.short?SSO=1, last accessed 18/09/25.
- 757 [27] Bouzakher-Ghomrasni N., Taché O., Leroy J., Feltin N., Testard F., Chivas-Joly C. 'Dimensional
758 measurement of TiO₂ (Nano) particles by SAXS and SEM in powder form' *Talanta* 2021, 234, p.122619.
- 759 [28] ISO/TS 21362:2018 'Nanotechnologies-Analysis of nano-Objects using asymmetrical-flow and centrifugal
760 field flow fractionation'.
- 761 [29] PCT/DZ02/00001, WO 02/085973 A1, 2002,
762 <https://patentimages.storage.googleapis.com/95/a4/96/b3961c6f59549d/WO2002085973A1.pdf>, last
763 accessed 18/09/2025.
- 764